

**A SEARCH FOR EQUIVALENCE IN EDUCATION CLASSIFICATIONS'
VARIANTS IN SOCIAL SURVEYS IN SLOVENIA.
A VALIDATION STUDY**

ESA RN21 „Quantitative Methods“ Midterm Conference

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JANEZ ŠTEBE, ADP, University of Ljubljana, 2012

- The problem,
- Background,
- Study design,
- Results,
- Conclusions.

The Problem

We would like to explore if difference in instrument form effects the validity of measurement

One of the key ,background` variables in social survey:

- Educational attainment

To the extend that validity of the different versions of measurements is affected, the association with criterion variables might be biased

The method effect could be interpreted as substantive conclusion

Background: New national classification of education

- There are two versions of the classification system, namely KLASIUS-SRV and KLASIUS-P.
- KLASIUS-SRV is of interest here: 3 level classification system based on level, stage of education and type of achievement.
- Complete classification with English categories text:

KLASIUS-SRV - Klasifikacije vrst izobraževalnih aktivnosti/izidov, V1
<http://www.stat.si/klasje/tabela.aspx?cvn=3967>

- The classification used is established as 'Official Statistical Standard' that is compulsory for administrative and statistical evidences.

While KLASIUS-SRV is not entirely compatible with the ISCED 1997, it contains crosswalks to it.

CENSUS 2011

- For the Census 2011 the data on educational attainment for total population of Slovenia was for the first time collected on the basis of available administrative and statistical sources .
 - KLASIUS-SRV was the version used in the Census 2011.
 - used to convert on a common base the data of valid classifications of education of different periods, and contained in different sources.
- Previous Censuses: individual statement of completion of level of education was recorded.
- 'subjective' bias in education recording is almost entirely removed.
- The Census information is also now up to date.
- For the mid period after the last Census it was only possible to assess a reliable up to date information by using sample information from continuous surveys with very large sample size, such as Labour Force Survey.

Population with at least tertiary education, age 20 <, by age and gender, Slovenia, 1. January 2011 (Census 2011, SURS)

CHART:

Danilo Dolenc, Darja Šter: **Izobrazba, Slovenija, 1. januar 2011**
– končni podatki. 29. december 2011, Prva objava

https://www.stat.si/novica_prikazi.aspx?id=4412

The new educational attainment measures in the ESS

- Based on ISCED-11
- National specific variables reformulated to meet the requirement of *edulvlb* Highest level of education

APPENDIX A1, EDUCATION, ESS5 - 2010 ed. e02_1

<http://ess.nsd.uib.no/ess/round5/>

As a consequence:

- Survey Data Series are affected:
 - Leading producer of academic surveys – CJMMK, national and international (SJM, ESS, ISSP, EVS etc.)
 - In particular, SJM survey changed the way education is measured: from traditional 7 categories to 12 categories classification
 - Greater precision is expected, some additional dimension could be taped by distinguishing, e.g. vocational vs. more general education

Mapping of new CSEV to EDULVLB (ESS Round 5 – 2010)

edulvlb Highest level of education	edlvdsi Highest level of education, Slovenia												
	0 Brez šolske izobrazbe	1 Nepopolna osnovna izobrazba	2 Osnovna izobrazba	3 Nižja ali srednja poklicna izobrazba	4 Srednja strokovna izobrazba	5 Srednja splošna izobrazba	6 Višja strokovna izobrazba, višješolska	7 Visokošolska strokovna izobrazba	8 Visokošolska univerzitetna izobrazba	9 Specializacija	10 Magisterij	11 Doktorat	
0 Not completed ISCED level 1	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
113 ISCED 1, completed primary education	0	49	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
213 General ISCED 2A, access ISCED 3A general/all 3	0	0	277	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
313 General ISCED 3A, access upper tier ISCED 5A/all 5	0	0	0	0	0	114	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
321 Vocational ISCED 3C >= 2 years, no access ISCED 5	0	0	0	294	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
323 Vocational ISCED 3A, access upper tier ISCED 5A/all 5	0	0	0	0	364	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
520 ISCED 5B short, advanced vocational qualifications	0	0	0	0	0	0	89	0	0	0	0	0	0
610 ISCED 5A medium, bachelor/equivalent from lower tier tertiary	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	51	0	0	0	0	0
620 ISCED 5A medium, bachelor/equivalent from upper/single tier	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	121	0	0	0	0
720 ISCED 5A long, master/equivalent from upper/single tier tertiary	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	17	0	0
800 ISCED 6, doctoral degree	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6

Mapping of old CSEV to EDULVLB (Own mapping, SJM091)

edulvlb Highest level of education	D5 Navedite zadnjo šolo, ki ste jo končali redno ali izredno:							
	1 nedokončan a osnovna šola	2 dokončana osnovna šola	3 nedokončan a strokovna ali srednja šola	4 dokončana 2 ali 3-letna strokovna šola	5 dokončana 4-letna srednja šola	6 nedokončan a višja ali visoka šola	7 dokončana 2-letna višja šola	8 dokončana visoka šola, fakulteta, akademija
,00 Not completed ISCED level 1	46	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
113,00 ISCED 1, completed primary education	0	181	14	0	0	0	0	0
313,00 General ISCED 3A, access upper tier ISCED 5A/all 5	0	0	0	0	345	43	0	0
321,00 Vocational ISCED 3C >= 2 years, no access ISCED 5	0	0	0	215	0	0	0	0
520,00 ISCED 5B short, advanced vocational qualifications	0	0	0	0	0	0	44	0
620,00 ISCED 5A medium, bachelor/equivalent from upper/single tier	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	169

Validation study design

Recently a couple of studies dealing with the question of validation of educational measurement in cross-national setting is being prepared: Hoffmeyer-Zlotnik & Warner (2007); Schneider (2010); Schroder & Ganzeboom (2012)

Our study is confined to national setting and seeks to assess the robustness of educational measurement variants as predictors

Construct validity is assessed by introducing two criterion variables for which we have reliable data at hand:

- Personal income
- Treiman SIOPS-08

Time period: 2009 – 2011, when change in measurement was introduced

The data used: Slovene LFS11, SJM111 (***Environment, ISSP 2010, Health, ISSP 2011***), SJM091 (***Religion, ISSP 2008, Social inequality, ISSP 2009***)

Mean SIOPS-08 by EDULVLB, different surveys

Mean Personal Income in EUR by EDULVLB, different surveys

Mean SIOPS-08 and Personal Income by Collapsed (7 categories) EDULVLB, different surveys

η^2

edulvlb Highest level of education	ads11	sjm111	sjm091
SIOPS-08	0,46	0,30	0,46
Income	0,24	0,28	0,31
edulvlb collapsed			
SIOPS-08	0,45	0,29	0,46
Income	0,22	0,26	0,31

r²

ADS11

SJM111

SJM091

SIOPS-08 Income SIOPS-08 Income SIOPS-08 Income

discussed	0,41	0,21	0,28	0,26	0,41	0,29
years of education (direct question)	0,19	0,12	0,25	0,23	0,39	0,28
hypothetical years	0,42	0,22	0,29	0,26	0,40	0,27
hwz	0,44	0,21	0,29	0,26	0,39	0,24
csev	0,45	0,23	0,28	0,27	0,39	0,28

Results so far:

New measure and the old one performs roughly
the same

Equivalence in construct validity is thus secured
across method/time/survey

Future studies could:

Extend the range of surveys and periods

Introduce different content areas of criterion
variables

Explore and confirm the equivalence in validity
thru time in international survey series

Tabela 10: Deleži prebivalcev Slovenije, starih 15 let in več, po stopnji izobrazbe, popisi 1961 - 1991

Izobrazba	Leto popisa			
	1961	1971	1981	1991
Skupaj - število prebivalcev	1 156 387	311 225	1 457 218	1 156 1628
- %	100	100	100	100
Brez šolske izobrazbe in končani 1-3 razredi osnovne šole	2,2	1,4	1,4	0,6
Končani 4-7 razredov osnovne šole	58,2	28,5	24,5	16,5
Osnovna šola	19,6	40,9	32,5	29,9
šola za KV in VKV delavce	13,1	17,6	22,0	19,4
Srednje šole	4,6	7,8	12,6	23,4
Višje, visoke šole in fakultete	1,8	1,3	5,9	8,8
Neznano	0,5	2,5	1,1	1,4

Tabela 2: Prebivalstvo, staro 15 ali več let, po izobrazbi in spolu, Slovenija, Popis 2002 in 1. januar 2011

Vir: SURS

	1. 1. 2011			Popis 2002		
	Skupaj %	Moški %	Ženske %	Skupaj %	Moški %	Ženske %
Skupaj	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
Brez izobrazbe	0,3	0,2	0,4	0,7	0,5	0,8
Nepopolna osnovnošolska	4,1	3,2	4,9	6,3	5,3	7,2
Osnovnošolska	24,7	21,2	28,2	26,1	21,1	30,8
Nižja poklicna	1,4	1,5	1,3	4,2	5,3	3,3
Srednja poklicna	21,7	28,5	15,1	22,9	29,6	16,7
Srednja strokovna, srednja splošna	30,2	30,0	30,4	26,9	25,7	27,9
Višješolska (prejšnja), višja strokovna	4,8	4,3	5,3	5,1	4,5	5,6
Visokošolska 1. stopnje, visokošolska strokovna (prejšnja) ipd.	3,3	2,5	4,1	0,5	0,4	0,6
Visokošolska 2. stopnje, visokošolska univerzitetna (prejšnja) ipd.	8,1	7,1	9,1	6,4	6,4	6,3
Magisterij znanosti (prejšnji) ipd.	0,8	0,9	0,8	0,7	0,8	0,6
Doktorat znanosti	0,4	0,6	0,3	0,3	0,4	0,2